

On Some Derivatives of 4-Phenylchroman.

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In order to study the properties of hydroxylated 4-phenylchromans which are of interest in their bearing on brazilin derivatives and their syntheses, it was considered desirable to prepare in the first place 7-methoxy-4-phenylchroman.

Our original plan was to prepare 2:4-dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylacrylic acid and to reduce it to the corresponding propionic acid and then over the ester to 2:4-dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylpropyl alcohol, the alcohol being converted subsequently into 7-methoxy-4-phenylchroman. It was found convenient to start with 7-methoxy-4-phenylcoumarin, prepared either by the action of acetyl chloride and acetic acid on 2:4-dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylacrylic acid or by condensing ethyl benzoylacetate with resorcinol monomethyl ether. Reduction of the coumarin with sodium and alcohol (Semmler, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2856) gives 2:4-dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylpropyl alcohol which on treatment with a saturated alcoholic solution of hydrochloric acid gives 7-methoxy-4-phenylchroman.

For the preparation of 7-methoxy-4-(3':4'-dimethoxy)phenylchroman, the starting point is the corresponding coumarin which may be obtained either from 2:4:3':4'-tetramethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylacrylic acid or by condensing ethyl veratroylacetate with resorcinol monomethyl ether, the second method giving a better yield.

Reduction with sodium and alcohol gave a product, probably the propyl alcohol derivative, which could not be obtained in an analysable condition. On heating with an alcoholic solution of hydrochloric acid saturated at 0° for three to four hours at 100°, the chroman was obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl β -Hydroxy-2:4-dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylpropionate.—2:4-Dimethoxybenzophenone (24 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (21 g.), zinc turnings (8.5 g.) and benzene dried over sodium (96 c.c.) were mixed in a flask fitted up with a reflux condenser and heated cautiously over the wire-gauze. Once started the reaction proceeds even without heating. It is complete in about three hours when the zinc goes almost entirely into solution and the originally light yellow mixture changes to a deep brown oily liquid. After cooling, the product is poured into ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid kept in a separating funnel and shaken vigorously. The benzene layer containing the condensation product is separated, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the benzene distilled off. The residue solidifies on cooling; needles from alcohol, m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 68.77; H, 7.17. $C_{19}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 69.09; H, 6.7 per cent.).

Ethyl 2:4-Dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylacrylate.—The dehydration of the oxy-ester could be effected neither by treatment with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate (Rupe and Busolt, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4537) nor by acetic anhydride and acetyl chloride (Stoermer and Friderici, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 333) but complete dehydration took place on subjecting it to dry distillation under diminished pressure. It melts first to a light brown liquid and then blackens. Water drops begin to distil and finally the cinnamic acid derivative distils as a reddish-brown thick oily liquid. On redistilling, a straw-coloured thick oily liquid, b.p. 228-232°/11 mm. was obtained. (Found: C, 72.64; H, 6.4. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 73.07; H, 6.41 per cent.).

2:4-Dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylacrylic Acid.—The acid was obtained by hydrolysing the ester (10 g.) with 25% methyl alcoholic potash (20 c.c.) on the water-bath under reflux for 24 hours. The reaction product was diluted with water and after removal of methyl alcohol by heating on the water-bath the unchanged ester was extracted with ether. The acid was precipitated by acidification with hydrochloric acid. Prisms from alcohol, m.p. 169-70°. (Found: C, 71.63; H, 6.01. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.83; H, 5.63 per cent.).

7-Methoxy-4-phenylcoumarin.—2:4-Dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylacrylic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (40 c.c.) in a stoppered bottle, freshly distilled acetyl chloride (10 c.c.) added and allowed to stand for 24 hours. The faint red colour of the mixture changed

gradually to deep violet. It was poured on crushed ice, the precipitate washed with sodium carbonate solution and recrystallised from alcohol as long needles, m.p. 114-15°. The same coumarin derivative was also obtained by methylation of the condensation product of ethyl benzoylacetate with resorcinol (Pechmann and Hanke, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 356). (Found: C, 75.91; H, 5.01. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.19; H, 4.76 per cent.).

2:4-Oxymethoxy-ββ-diphenyl propyl Alcohol.—7-Methoxy-4-phenylcoumarin (5 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) previously distilled over metallic calcium, in a flask fitted with a condenser and a soda-lime guard-tube and metallic sodium (15 g.) added all at once. The reaction is very vigorous but subsides to some extent within five minutes, the vessel is then placed in an oil-bath, heated to 140-50° and the reaction is allowed to proceed till all the sodium had dissolved. For the success of the operation the system should be perfectly dry and the reaction mixture should in no case be allowed to solidify, further 50 to 75 c.c. of absolute alcohol being added if necessary. The reaction is complete in about three to four hours when, after cooling, 100 c.c. of water are added and the ethyl alcohol removed by passing steam. The residue is acidified with hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether distilled off. The residue is distilled under diminished pressure, b.p. 253°-254°/10 mm. It was found to solidify on standing for nearly a month; m.p. 77-78°. (Found: C, 74.01; H, 7.01. $C_{16}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 74.41; H, 5.97 per cent.).

7-Methoxy-4-phenylchroman.—The alcohol (3 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas and heated in a sealed tube at 100° for six hours. After cooling, the contents are poured into water, the alcohol removed by heating on the water-bath, cooled, and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with dilute caustic soda solution, dehydrated with anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled under diminished pressure, b.p. 203°-204°/10 mm. (Found: C, 79.7; H, 7.17. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 6.66 per cent.).

2:4-Dimethoxy-ββ-diphenylpropionic Acid.—The corresponding acrylic acid was dissolved in the calculated quantity of 10% caustic soda solution and sodium amalgam (4.5 g. sodium in 180 g. of mercury) was gradually added in course of 3-4 hours with frequent shaking. The alkalinity was kept down by the addition of small

quantities of hydrochloric acid from time to time. After standing overnight the solution was decanted. On acidification an ash-coloured thick oil was precipitated which soon solidified. Rectangular plates from alcohol, m.p. 129-30°. (Found: C, 71.05; H, 6.48. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 71.33; H, 6.29 per cent.).

Ethyl 2:4-Dimethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylpropionate.—The ester was prepared by saturating an absolute alcoholic solution of the acid with dry hydrochloric acid gas and heating under reflux on the water-bath for an hour. The ester was precipitated with water, dissolved in ether, filtered, washed with sodium carbonate solution. On evaporating the ether it remained as an oil which was re-dissolved in petroleum ether. On cooling in a freezing mixture it separated in flattened needles, m.p. 54°. (Found: C, 72.48; H, 7.19. $C_{19}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 72.61; 7.06 per cent.).

2:4:3':4'-Tetramethoxybenzophenone.—Aluminium chloride (10 g.) was added to a mixture of veratroyl chloride (10 g.) and resorcinol dimethyl ether (30 c.c.) with constant shaking, the temperature being kept below 40°. The excess of resorcinol dimethyl ether was removed by repeated extraction with carbon bisulphide and finally the condensation product was decomposed cautiously by warming with dilute hydrochloric acid on the water-bath for ten minutes. The ketone was treated for a few minutes with hot caustic soda solution and the residue recrystallised from alcohol; prisms, m.p. 126°. (Found: C, 67.19; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 67.54; H, 5.96 per cent.).

2:4:3':4'-Tetramethoxy- $\beta\beta$ -diphenylacrylic Acid.—2:4:3':4'-Tetramethoxybenzophenone (10 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (7 g.), zinc turnings (2.8 g.) and benzene dried over sodium (50 c.c.) were heated cautiously under reflux over the wire-gauze. The reaction is complete in about three hours when the product assumed a brown jelly-like appearance. It was cooled and decomposed by shaking with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid in a separating funnel. The benzene layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the benzene evaporated when a thick brown oily liquid was obtained. A portion of the condensation product (5 g.) was hydrolysed with 25% methyl alcoholic potash (10 c.c.) on the water-bath for twenty-four hours. Another portion was dry-distilled in *vacuo* and the distillate (5 g.) hydrolysed as before. The products were found to be identical, both melting at 157° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: C, 66.40; H, 6.23. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 66.28; H, 5.81 per cent.).

2: 4:3':4'-*Tetramethoxy-ββ-diphenylpropionic Acid*.—The acrylic acid derivative (4.5 g.) was dissolved in the calculated quantity of 10% caustic soda solution and sodium amalgam made by dissolving sodium (1.2 g.) in mercury (45 g.) was gradually added with frequent shaking. The addition is complete in about two hours and the mixture is allowed to stand overnight at the ordinary temperature. The alkaline liquid is decanted off and acidified with hydrochloric acid when the dihydro-acid is precipitated as an oil which soon solidifies; plates from alcohol, m.p. 121°. (Found: C, 66.06; H, 6.6. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 65.89; H, 6.35 per cent.).

7-Methoxy-4-(3':4'-dimethoxy) phenylcoumarin.—2: 4:3': 4'-Tetramethoxy-ββ-diphenylacrylic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.), cooled to about 5° and freshly distilled acetyl chloride (5 c.c.) was added and allowed to stand at ordinary temperature for 24 hours. The product which had assumed a resinous appearance was poured into crushed ice and the precipitate filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 163°. As the yield was very small, an alternative method of preparation was attempted. Ethyl veratroylacetate was prepared by condensing veratroyl chloride with ethyl sodioacetate in ethereal solution (*Beilstein*, *II, 958). The product was hydrolysed with 10% ammonium hydroxide solution at 40°-50° for 15 minutes. The veratroylacetic ester separated as an oil which was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The ester could not be obtained in an analysable condition as it boils with decomposition above 200° at 10 mm. It is freed from its lower-boiling impurities by heating at 140° for half an hour at 10 mm. The purified ester (5 g.) was mixed with resorcinol monomethyl ether (2.6 g.), cooled well in ice and ice-cold pure sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was added in about one and a half hours' time. The mixture was allowed to stand in a well-stoppered bottle and after 12 hours poured into crushed ice. The semi-solid mass was treated with dilute caustic soda solution and crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 163° which is not depressed by admixture with the product obtained by the first method. (Found: C, 69.10; H, 5.43. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 69.23; H, 5.12 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-4(3': 4'-dimethoxy)phenylcoumarin.—Purified ethyl veratroyl acetate (2 g.) and resorcinol (1.1 g.) was treated with sulphuric acid as in the previous case and the product crystallised from alcohol; needles, m.p. 236°. (Found: C, 69.72; H, 5.14. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.45; H, 4.69 per cent.). Methylation with dimethyl

sulphate gives 7-methoxy-4(3' : 4'-dimethoxy)phenylcoumarin, m.p. 163°.

7-Methoxy-4(3' : 4'-dimethoxy)phenylchroman.—The coumarin (5 g.) was dissolved in 150 c.c. absolute alcohol and metallic sodium (15 g.) added in three instalments. The mixture is heated in an oil-bath at 140-50° for three hours when nearly the whole of the sodium practically dissolved. Rectified spirit (50 c.c.) was next added to dissolve any unreacted sodium. The mixture was dissolved in water and the alcohol removed by passing steam. It was then cooled, acidified with hydrochloric acid when a viscous oil was precipitated. The oil was taken up with ether and the extract treated twice with 2% caustic soda solution. On acidification with hydrochloric acid a gummy precipitate was obtained which solidified after 24 hours but which could not be crystallised from any solvent. The crude product was heated in a sealed tube at 100° with alcohol saturated with hydrochloric acid, for 3—4 hours. The reaction product was then poured into water, extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with 2% sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted and partially demethylated product, dried with calcium chloride and the ether evaporated. As the substance showed no tendency to solidify even after long standing it was distilled under diminished pressure when the chroman was obtained as an oil, b.p. 263°-266°/4 mm. (Found: C, 71.73; H, 7.23. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 72.00; H, 6.67 per cent.).

The work will be continued.